

Early Career Academic's Odyssey: A Narrative Study of her Professional Identity Construction.

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Recent decades have seen a major transformation of the Spanish university system caused by changes introduced in the teaching staff evaluation procedure in which research has been prioritized. As a result, there has been a growing interest in studying how these procedures impact the way in which early career academics construct their professional identity. In this vein, this article aims to analyze how the professional identity of this group is constructed and developed in the current context of Higher Education. To this end, a single case study was conducted, applying a biographical-narrative approach. The results show how professional identity development has become polarized in terms of initial rejection to full acceptance of the demands of modern academia.

Consequently, professional practices have also been affected by the prioritization of research over teaching, leading to the development of unethical practices to maintain competitiveness. All of these effects have contributed to high levels of stress and job dissatisfaction. Furthermore, maternity is also seen as an obstacle to female academics' professional and academic development. Finally, our findings highlight the need for policies that provide full support aimed at helping young researchers live balanced professional lives.

Keywords: professional identity; higher education; case study; early career academic; female academic.

Introduction

Early Career Academics are the group of academics (researchers or/and teachers) who are at the stage between beginning their academic career and securing a stable position (Nicholas et al., 2019). This group is considered one of the most vulnerable in the academic world (Castelló et al., 2015; Acker and Webber, 2017). In recent years, this situation has worsened due to two fundamental factors: the increase in job insecurity and precariousness in this sector and the new demands of the knowledge-based society (Shams, 2019; Saura and Bolívar, 2019). Broadly speaking, these changes are impacting the way in which this group performs their professional roles, their social and family

relationships, their health, and, as a consequence, the development of their professional identity (Dugas et al.,2019; Huang and Guo,2019).

Professional identity can be defined as a dynamic process that results from the interaction between each subject's self-conception and their relationship with 1) the characteristics of the political, economic, social, and professional context, 2) their life and professional experiences, and 3) their personal values, beliefs, and motivations (Bolívar,2014). In this sense, we understand the term from an *interactionist perspective*, i.e., as a subjective and social construction (Dubar,2007).

Concerning the professional identity of academics, several studies point to the broader social context of Higher Education (HE) as one of the most influential elements (Lankveld et al., 2017). For instance, Zabalza (2011) argues that the identity construction of university teachers does not occur in isolation from the time and context in which they are immersed, which are currently characterized by the use of practices and values typical of the new public management system.

Although the identity of an academic will undergo multiple transformations throughout their professional career (Djarasimovic and Villani, 2019), their early experiences in the professional context have a significant influence on their future professional identity (Gewerc, 2001). For this reason, and out of concern for the impact that these young academics can have on science and the future of universities (Crew, 2020) recent years have seen a significant increase in the number of studies conducted in this field of research (Mula-Falcón et al., 2021).

In this regard, studies such as those by Monreo and Liesa (2020), Olson and Jiang (2020), and Djarasimovic and Villani (2019) have addressed this issue in various parts of the world and through the use of different methodologies. However, there are

hardly any biographical-narrative studies (Mula-Falcón et al., 2021), a methodology that is considered the most appropriate for studying identity, as it allows for a holistic understanding of its construction by addressing its dynamic, contextual, and multifactorial nature (Domingo and Bolívar, 2019).

Therefore, the present research uses a single case study which, from a hermeneutic-narrative approach and using the biographical method (Bolívar and Domingo, 2019), aims to analyze and understand the impact of the social context of HE on the construction and development of the professional identity of young academics. In this case, we focus on the Spanish context, given the scarcity of scientific production in this area of research in Spain (Mula-Falcón et al., 2021).

In short, this study aims to answer the following research question: *what impact does the new university reality have on the construction of a young academic's professional identity?* To address this question, we analyzed the main milestones and protagonists that have shaped the construction of professional identity, as well as the opinions and emotions generated from experiences lived in the academic sphere. We begin by describing the reality of the modern university. Next, the methodology is presented, the research process is outlined, and the main results are highlighted. Finally, we will discuss the results in relation to the previous literature and draw a series of conclusions.

The wider social context of higher education.

For over two decades, European higher education has been subjected to a series of policies to standardize its processes and outcomes. The main objective of these policies is to facilitate the homogenization of this sector, enhancing labor mobility and better responding to the needs of the European labor market (Brøgger, 2019). In short, the aim

is to implement a series of changes aimed at contributing to economic progress by improving the quality of this sector (Bermúdez-Aponte and Laspalas,2017).

To this end, and aside from various structural changes such as the increase in mobility programs, the introduction of the "Undergraduate+Postgraduate" formula, and the credit-based system, we have observed the development of a set of accountability policies based on the proliferation of evaluation processes and the parallel development of a significant incentive-reward regime (Dougherty and Natow, 2019). In this respect, recent decades have seen a significant growth of these evaluation processes focused on different aspects of academia (e.g., teaching, curricula, and mobility schemes). The outcomes of these processes are thus determining factors when it comes to closing or opening degrees, obtaining funding, or increasing the social prestige of the institutions (Gill and Donoghue, 2016).

In the specific case of university academics, these processes have taken shape in the form of professional performance evaluations characterized by the importance they assign to research activity over other duties (Fernández-Cano,2021). Moreover, the fact that these valuations impact access, permanence, and promotion in university positions as well as the likelihood of securing research funding or even salary supplements (Ma and Ladisch,2019), means that research activity becomes the driving force behind the work of academics (Herrán and Villena, 2016). Thus, research has become essential for survival in academia (Bermúdez-Aponte and Laspalas,2017).

Recent years have seen a significant proliferation of these assessment and benchmarking processes worldwide, although with some differences, such as their frequency or the level of funding involved (Browing, Thompson, and Dawson, 2017). International examples include *Excellence in Research for Australia* (Australia),

Performance-Based Research Fund Quality Evaluation (New Zealand), *Research Assessment Exercise* (Hong Kong); *Research Excellence Framework* (UK), *Initiatives d'Excellence* (France), *STAR METRICS* (USA) or *Excellenzinitiative* (Germany). As a result, this new scenario fosters an environment in which market interests, competitiveness, and individualization, are beginning to undermine the academic ethos based on principles of autonomy, reflection, and freedom (Bermúdez-Aponte and Laspalas, 2017).

The Spanish case

In Spain, evaluations emerged from the original Organic Law on Universities (2001) and, subsequently, with the New Organic Law for Universities (2007). These laws encouraged the creation of the National Agency for Evaluation and Accreditation (ANECA in its Spanish acronym) in 2002. The main objective of this body is to "contribute to the improvement of the quality of the higher education system through the evaluation, certification, and accreditation of teaching, teaching staff, and institutions" (ANECA, 2020).

Three different programs are used for university accreditation: *PEP*, *Academia*, and *CNEAI*. Of these, *PEP* (Teacher Evaluation Programme for recruitment) has the greatest influence on young academics, as it evaluates those who wish to access permanent positions in Spanish universities.¹ (Art.48, LOMLOU).

If we look at the criteria for a positive *PEP*, there is a clear imbalance between the professional functions (60 % in research versus 40 % in other activities including

¹ Permanent positions in Spanish universities involve teaching and research.

teaching, management, and training). Similarly, publications in academic journals account for 58.4% of the 60 points available in the research evaluation. Therefore, in the case of young researchers, their ability to produce scientific articles will largely determine their likelihood of passing the *PEP* and gaining access to permanent positions. Thus, young Spanish academics are under intense pressure to increase their scientific productivity to gain access to a university post. All of these challenges, together with their precarious and unstable employment status, means that young researchers have become the most vulnerable group within academia (Ylijoki and Henriksson, 2017).

Despite these circumstances, recent years have seen an increase in the number of young researchers, as evidenced by a rise in the number of applications for permanent position contracts (from 4000 applications in 2005 to 12000 in 2020) (ANECA, 2021). Consequently, a highly competitive and individualized environment is developing (Bermúdez-Aponte and Laspalas, 2017) that is particularly affecting the professional development of this group of academics.

Methodology

This work aims to analyze the impact of the current university climate on the construction of the professional identity of young academics. Furthermore, this research aims to contribute to the existing group of studies focused on this issue in the Spanish context (Castelló et al., 2015; Monreo and Liesa, 2020).

Given our approach to identity based on a social, interpretative, and interactionist perspective, the meaning individuals give to their history is central to our research. Within this perspective, professional identity is not only defined by the line of work but is also a social and personal construct based on experiences, feelings, and emotions. Therefore,

the hermeneutic-narrative approach with a biographical orientation (Bolívar and Domingo, 2019) is a key feature of this study.

The narrative approach is considered essential for understanding professional identities. In this respect, Craig (2007) considers narrative the most appropriate medium for studying personal experiences, allowing us to capture details (e.g., emotions, desires, and motivations,) that would otherwise be difficult to express. Specifically, this research adopts a hermeneutic narrative approach so that data collection is based on individuals' interpretations and the meanings they attach to their own experiences (Goodson et al., 2016). This approach allows for an understanding of the psychological complexity of individuals' narratives, including the conflicts and dilemmas inherent in their stories (Bolívar, 2002). This framework — rather than establishing cause-effect relationships — aims to give meaning to and understand the lived and narrated experience. To this end, we adopted a biographical approach through life stories in which the objective is not only to determine what happened but to also delve into the self-conception on the meaning of what happened and its impact on the self and its projected future (Bolívar and Domingo, 2019). In this case, and as a variant of the traditional biographical-narrative approach, this study will only focus on a particular period of the subject's life (Djersimovic and Villani, 2019), that is, the early part of their career.

Key participant

According to Bolívar and Domingo (2019), life stories must focus on singular cases, the choice of which must comply with a series of requirements, including relevance to the study's objective and the degree of exemplarity. For this reason, in this study, we show an example of a paradigmatic case, i.e., a case that shows certain typical characteristics of a particular group in an exemplary (or prototypical) way (Flyvberg, 2006; Giménez, 2012). In this study, the characteristics were determined from a broader quantitative

project that provides the framework for this research and in which all public universities in the region of Andalusia participated. This project identified a very characteristic identity profile in young academics between 25 and 35 years old who had completed their doctoral studies. Therefore, based on these fundamental characteristics and to meet formal criteria (accessibility/participation), non-probabilistic snowball sampling was employed. Furthermore, this procedure allowed us to identify and interview several potential study participants. Finally, as a result of all the interviews, we selected the case of Margarita (pseudonym), a young female academic who met all the desired study characteristics for the purposes of our analysis.

Margarita is a 31-year-old academic. During her bachelor's and master's studies, she received various research initiation grants through which she was introduced to the world of research. After this period, she began her doctoral studies as a beneficiary of the Aid for University Teacher Training. During this time, she taught for more than 200 hours in various subjects of undergraduate degrees. She also completed six months of doctoral research visits in different European universities, all financed by the Ministry of Science. After finishing her Ph.D., she passed *PEP* evaluations and worked as a teaching substitute at different universities while supervising several final degree projects. She is currently awaiting the outcomes of applications for permanent university contracts. Her CV includes more than fifteen research articles.

Data collection and analysis

The information was collected through in-depth conversational interviews based on accounts of experience and shared reflections and arguments on the emerging themes through a cascading process of reflexive deepening until thematic saturation (Kelchtermans, 2016). This in-depth reflexive process consisted of a cycle of three

interviews, each of which expanded on issues raised in the previous session. In this regard, the first part of each interview was devoted to clarifying and delving deeper into various aspects of the previous interview. This procedure served as a process of dialectical validation of the information collected (Kletcherman, 2016), i.e., the dialogue between the researcher and the researched about previous sessions allowed for reflection, deepening, and triangulation of the information. At the same time, a research diary was used in each interview to record those aspects that were difficult to perceive in the narration itself (e.g., irony, non-verbal language,).

Each of the interviews dealt with different issues. The first interview (one hour) consisted of a descriptive phase in which Margarita was invited to tell her story and recount her experiences from her early days in academia. In this session, only clarifying questions were asked. In the time between this and the next interview, a timeline was drawn up jointly with the researcher, positioning the elements, milestones, or people who, according to her, were the most influential. In the second interview (divided into two one-hour sessions), we delved deeper into each aspect pointed out in the timeline. To this end, Margarita was asked to reflect on the impact of these aspects through the use of generative questions such as: *tell me how you felt, what you thought, how it affected you.*

The interviews were recorded and transcribed. All interviews were conducted in Spanish, this being the mother tongue of both the study participant and researchers. Therefore, the entire process of transcription, analysis, and writing of the text was also carried out in this language. Once the process was completed, the text was translated by a specialist translator, with clarifications made by the researchers on certain terminology.

The data were subjected to a narrative analysis (Bolívar, 2002), allowing themes to emerge from Margarita's narration and reflection. Therefore, in the analysis, the researchers focused on significantly deciphering the relevant components and dimensions

that impacted the participant's identity during her academic life. The aim of this approach was to generate a singular narrative, expressing the subject's voice without manipulation and, at the same time, forming a temporal and thematic plot that would allow us to provide a comprehensive response to the object of study. Thus, rather than establishing cause-effect relationships, we were able to make sense of and understand the lived and narrated experience. To this end, the Nvivo 12 software provided an organized and structured procedure for coding, an essential element for successful qualitative analysis.

Ethical considerations

Several ethical issues were considered. First, informed consent was given after the participant was informed of the research objectives, the study's requirements, their right to anonymity, and the possibility of leaving the research any time they wished. Second, a pseudonym was used to ensure anonymity, and some potentially identifying information was omitted. Finally, it should also be noted that the participant verified all the information collected and its reconstruction through the interpretation process.

Author positionality statement

The present study was conducted by two authors with different profiles (male/female, young/veteran, unstable/stable position). These characteristics allow them to be situated on a continuum between the outsider and insider positioning of the culture under study. The latter provides benefits such as direct access to the culture under study, a greater degree of confidence on the part of the participants, and a reduction in culture shock (Holmes, 2020). However, to avoid judgment and bias, increase the degree of objectivity, and avoid the manipulation of the original discourse according to the interests of the researcher, from an ontological point of view, priority has been given to an *emic* conception in which the discourse of the subject is of central importance (Bolívar, 2002). In this regard, the researcher's task was to order and make sense of the participant's

discourse without alteration. To do this, the researchers organized and temporally unified the discourse around themes to help understand the narrated experiences.

Results

Throughout Margarita's life, we can observe a significant transformation in her conception of academia, in the development of her professional practice, and, therefore, in the construction of her professional identity. To facilitate the analysis, we divided Margarita's life into three different stages: 1) Start and shock, 2) Acceptance and subordination, and 3) Fatigue and disillusionment (current). In each of these stages, we will analyze the milestones that have contributed most to developing her current professional identity. We will also highlight the emotions and opinions of the young researcher concerning different aspects that characterize the current situation in universities. Furthermore, to present our results visually, Table 1 shows her professional biogram, highlighting most significant moments and their impact on her identity.

Table 1. Margarita's Biogram.

Stages	Description	Milestone, key character, theme or leitmotiv	Personal/professional impact
<i>Start and Shock</i>	First contacts with the world of academia (research initiation grants and first year of doctoral studies).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First contacts with university teaching staff evaluation processes. • Lack of guidance, direction, and training. • Environment characterised by enmity, opportunism, individualistic practices, and corruption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idealised vision of academia. • Feelings of loneliness and dissatisfaction. • Disappointment with the working environment. • Demystification of her ideal of academia and disappointment with her working environment.
<i>Acceptance and submission</i>	Final years of doctoral studies and <i>PEP</i> evaluation period.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colleagues' advice about academia (teaching and publishing). • Increased pressure to raise scientific output. • Awareness of the importance of scientific 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformation of her professional practices. • Publishing becomes the primary goal. • Teaching practices far removed from her initial conception (relegated to

		production for her continuity in academia.	second place and seen as an obstacle). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of unconventional practices to increase scientific output. • Sleep problems, anxiety, stress, and physical health problems. • Constant feelings of guilt for underachievement
<i>Fatigue and Disillusionment.</i>	From the completion of her thesis to the present day.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High job insecurity: temporary contracts at different universities. • Consideration of other employment options. • Internal debate generated about the decision to become a mother. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disillusionment and job and professional dissatisfaction. • Hope for a change in her professional practices when she secures a tenured position. • Fear of losing her ideals. • Fear of motherhood, which is viewed as a professional obstacle.

Source: Author's own.

First stage: Start and shock.

Margarita began her university career with the help of several research initiation grants. These experiences encouraged her to enroll in doctoral studies and apply for University Teacher Training Grants. However, in the beginning, her main interest in starting her academic career lay in her intellectual concerns as well as her social commitment:

I liked to read, to reflect, to learn. I wanted to reach the end of the road of education and try to do my bit for society: in research, by contributing something to improve the situation in my field; and in teaching, by influencing future professionals, innovating, and avoiding all those things I didn't like about my teachers.

At the time, Margarita had a vision of academia that closely resembled that of the Humboldtian philosophy, characterized by principles of freedom, reflection, and social service (Martínez and Estaban, 2005):

For me, the university was a place of prestige. I had idealized it; I had that vision of the university professor that you see in films and that everyone has: that wise, intelligent

person who influences society and who, on top of that, has an impact on and makes a mark on their students.

However, her first contact with the world of academia helped to change her viewpoint. Among the main reasons for this change, she mentions disillusionment with the training of her peers and "superiors" or the observation of unethical practices far removed from her university ideals (e.g., neglect of teaching and students, class preparation, training, paying to publish, taking advantage of Ph.D. students' work, and bad authorship practices). She soon realized that this was a consequence of the high competitiveness and pressure to publish generated by the evaluation processes:

I have nothing against the evaluation of university professors. The problem lies in the method: they give much more weight to research than to teaching, and, on top of that, they don't care about the article's content; the important thing is where it is published. And this generates consequences, it is obvious, now the objective is to publish, not even to research, it is to publish.

In this first period, the most common feelings are loneliness and dissatisfaction. Loneliness is caused by a lack of guidance, direction, and training. Despite having a supervisor or different training programs at her university, these did not have any formative or guiding impact on her:

No one supports you; no one teaches you, no one. You are alone in the face of everything: your first publication, your first proofreading, your teaching, your internships... You are alone in the battle. I feel alone, very alone, to tell you the truth. There is no one to help you. You are alone, and you have to learn to survive by falling down and getting back on your feet. You feel you have to respond at a level for which you are not trained and for which you don't have enough support. I have had no guidance, no direction, nothing. Not by the university, not by the ministry, not by my own supervisor.

And, dissatisfaction was evident, caused by two factors: the demystification of her idealized view of academia and disappointment with her working environment.

Regarding the demystification of academic ideals:

I used to be in love with research and teaching, but when you go in and see what research really is and what it means to be a university teacher nowadays, you fall out of love. I like to do things well, not the way they force us to do them.

Finally, in terms of her working environment, Margarita highlights the enormous disappointment in observing the animosity, opportunism, individualistic practices, and corruption that are present:

As far as the work context is concerned, ... I don't even want to talk about it. That's where I've had a big disappointment. First, because of some colleagues, everyone goes their own way, there is no sharing, and it is difficult to make friends; they see you as a rival. And this lack of camaraderie affects you. Second, because there are so many leeches out there who take advantage of your work and then go around taking all the credit for it. And thirdly, because of the mafia. If you belong to the department's favorite group, everything goes smoothly, but if you belong to the other group... they make life impossible for you. They take it out on you for quarrels that happened even before I was born.

Second stage: Acceptance and submission

In this second stage (final years of doctoral studies and *PEP* evaluation period), Margarita's account shows a gradual shift toward acceptance of the new demands of academia. During this process, her colleague's advice was fundamental:

I didn't agree with these principles and was not willing to accept them, but my research colleague insisted: "*These are the rules of the game, and there are two options, you accept them, and you have a slim chance, or you don't, and you say goodbye to the university*" So little by little I realized that everybody was doing it, and that, if in the end I intended to stay, I had to adapt.

During this period, the young academic underlines the enormous pressure she was under to increase her scientific output. In this sense, Margarita recounts how she was sometimes more focused on getting published (on whatever the topic) than on the development of studies related to the subject of her thesis:

You realize that this has become a race to see who has the biggest CV, well, to see who has the most articles. Because if you don't, you can't get accredited (favorably evaluated), and you can't get places. And this generates a lot of pressure. So sometimes, I completely forgot about my thesis to be able to publish as much as possible, whatever it was about.

As a result, both her research and teaching were affected. Concerning research, she reports the development of unconventional practices:

That need to publish to stay makes you start to lower the quality of your articles or start to develop practices you are not proud of: bad authorship practices, falsifying some data, or even paying to publish. But what else would I do? How would I survive?

Concerning teaching, there has been a significant shift toward practices far removed from her initial conception of good teaching:

My colleague once said to me: "*you do your research, teaching is improvised, that's why we have speech. You are evaluated by how many JCRs² you have, and for teaching with a couple of favorable evaluations, you have enough, so don't fail too many and don't make them think or work too much*". And, of course, at first, you resist, and you prepare your classes, and you look for innovative methodologies. But little by little, you see your environment, learn, and realize that it takes up too much of your time for what is really going to feed you: research. So, you leave teaching to one side and start to improvise.

² JCR stands for Journal citation Report. This is a database that ranks and evaluates the impact and relevance of scientific journals.

At this stage, sleep problems, anxiety, stress, and even physical health problems became frequent in her life:

I haven't had a good night's sleep for a long time; I don't rest. And at that time, I was working all day long, and my head was spinning. Because of the stress, they put me in a splint, my jaw and my teeth were getting smashed. And well: problems with my period, hair loss, sores... in short, a panorama.

However, of all the consequences, Margarita highlights the enormous feeling of guilt that was present throughout this time:

The worst thing by far is the constant guilt for not being at work or writing articles all the time. Sometimes I've gone out to dinner and felt guilty for not working. Or I've sat down to watch a movie, and that feeling has made me stop and start writing. And even once, I had a complicated family situation, and I wasn't performing, but I still felt bad, very bad. I still feel that way today.

Current time: Fatigue and Disillusionment.

This stage covers the period from completing her thesis to the present day. At the moment, Margarita is doing substitutions³ in different universities, while she awaits the decisions regarding her applications for permanent positions. During this period, she highlights the enormous job insecurity generated by her temporary contracts, as well as the high level of dissatisfaction with the work she has been doing:

Right now, I'm a bit fed up and very tired. First, because after all I've done and after all I've achieved, I'm doing substitutions and with a salary that doesn't even give me enough to live on. And secondly because I don't feel satisfied with what I'm doing. I don't feel like a good teacher doing everything I have always criticized. And much less do I feel like a good researcher because how can we call ourselves researchers with what we do?

³ Temporary position to cover the services of someone on leave.

Her vision of academia in this period is completely different from the one she had at the beginning of her career. If, in the beginning, she was excited about starting her university career, now the opposite is the case:

The university has become a competition; there is no more reflection, no more discussion, no more quality writing. Now the objective is the JCR; students don't even enter into the equation. I've even been in a project meeting, and the conversation focused on organizing ourselves to publish as much as possible. And I'm not going to lie to you, all this has meant that lately, I've been thinking more and more about giving it up, looking for something alternative outside of here.

Despite this, in Margarita's story there seems to be a certain hope for a change in her future once she has secured a stable position. However, there is a certain fear of losing her principles:

I am left with the hope of being that academic that I wanted to be once I have my assistantship. But then I look at the other assistants, and I say... "*normal, they have got used to a reality and have made it their truth* ." I'm afraid that by the time I get the position, it will be too late, and I will have forgotten the goal I had when I came here.

Finally, the highlight of this period is undoubtedly the important internal conflict she generated about the decision to become a mother. While it is true that this aspect has always been present, it has been accentuated at this stage:

I'm getting older, and I'm going to be an old mum in the end, if I can be one. I have always thought about when would be the best time to have a child. Sometimes I would say to myself, "*when I finish my doctorate*," other times, "*when you have an assistant position*," and others, "*no, it would be better when you become a tenured professor* ." And in the end, you realize that you put it off because you are afraid of the time it will take away from you. Yes, I'll have my months off work, but then, who writes three articles a month when you have a baby who won't let you sleep? I've been thinking about it for a long time: when is the right time?

Discussion and conclusions

This study has analysed the construction and development of the professional identity of a young female academic in the context of the modern university climate using a hermeneutic-narrative approach and the biographical method. This study allowed us to highlight milestones that have impacted the development of her current identity, as well as the emotions and opinions of the young researcher concerning various aspects that characterize the current panorama of the university world.

Her story reveals a transformation in the development of her professional practice, her vision of academia, and, therefore, the construction of her professional identity. Throughout her academic life, this young researcher has experienced a significant internal debate, which Dubar (2007) referred to as an *identity crisis*, generated by the clash between her traditional vision of academia characterized by principles of reflection, freedom, and social service, and those that prevail in the current university scenario, i.e., market interests, competitiveness, and the individualization of work. These results are compatible with those reported by Shams (2019) and Petersen (2016). The latter describes a unique case study of an Australian academic in which there is a clash between her strategic efforts to secure project funding and her ideals and desires. However, research by Dugas et al. (2020) and Guzmán-Valenzuela and Martínez (2016) has highlighted another type of internal debate that we also found in our participant. In particular, we are referring to the conflict that arises from their search for achieving a balance between carrying out their duties and prioritizing research activities.

As a result, there has been an evolution in the development of Margarita's identity. As mentioned by Ylojiki and Ursin (2013) and Huang and Guo (2019), the current university climate encourages the development of academic identities characterized by dynamism, reshaping, and a high — sometimes vertigo-inducing — pace of change.

In this regard, we observed in Margarita an initial identity characterized by the rejection of the new demands of academia, the search for a balance between teaching and research roles, and the supremacy of traditional values. This identity is known in the literature as the Identity of Resistance or Refusal (Ylijoki,2014). However, with the passage of time, the gradual acceptance of the new forms of academia became evident in our participant. Again, as in the Telkeen (2016) study, the work environment played a key role in shaping this change.

As a result, in the second stage, we observed an identity characterized by the predominance of research over teaching, and a tendency to participate and accommodate to the system, and even the development of previously rejected practices to increase the number and pace of production. This observation is consistent with Fanelli's (2009) meta-analysis, which seems to show a certain prevalence of scientific misconduct. According to Djarasimovic and Villani (2019) and Harvey (2020), this is due to the need to survive in the university world or to obtain funding/grants. Despite this submission, we observed in Margarita a certain critical component of the system that develops alongside unconventional research practices, which agrees with the findings of Acker and Webber (2017), Huang and Guo (2019), and Jiménez (2019). These authors refer to this identity as the Identity of the Expelled Academic or the Identity of the Academic Manager. Finally, throughout this stage, we also observed how the work environment exerts an enormous influence on the way in which our participant carries out her academic duties. This coincides with the study by Olson and Jiang (2020), which demonstrated how a strong research climate contributes to a lower dedication to teaching, which is exactly what has been observed in the present case.

Conclusively, we observed a last stage, characterized by a notable shift from the previous identity towards one characterized by an unconscious submission due to the

normalization of this current reality (Cannizzo,2017), as also reported by Saura and Bolívar (2019). These authors speak of a "new neoliberal academic subject" characterized by a high level of "somatization of neoliberalism in the self" (p.19) that produces a subject unconsciously subordinated to the system. This system produces self-control processes (Luengo and Saura,2014) leading to self-government dynamics that make academics take responsibility for their own outcomes (Saura and Bolívar,2019). Therefore, it is not surprising that the continuous feeling of guilt in our participant (which Byung-Chul Han also refers to in his work, "The Tired Society", 2010) eventually produces these high levels of stress and anxiety. Furthermore, in line with Acker and Webber's (2017) studies, our participant also expresses a sense of hope that there will be a change in her conditions once she has secured a tenured position.

Finally, we highlight the internal conflict generated by the issue of motherhood. Our study shows how being a mother is seen as an obstacle that impacts not only the professional but, particularly, the personal identity of our participant. According to Engen, Bleijenbergh, and Beijer (2019), the fear of combining family and work directly impacts female academics. These findings align with Abetz's (2019) research, which found that the fear of decreasing scientific productivity led female academics to consider delaying motherhood by putting their career goals first.

Ultimately, this study shows how the new forms of academia have impacted our participant's work, health, and professional identity. The fact that access and advancement depend on scientific production leads to the neglect of other functions and the development of unethical research practices. As a result, the university environment is increasingly moving away from its traditional pillars and is instead being driven by market principles such as competitiveness, productivity, and economics. Thus, what began as policies to improve quality seem to have developed into a system that represents

quite the opposite. Therefore, more than ever, cultural and organizational changes are needed to help young researchers develop balanced and fulfilling personal and professional lives. Along these lines, for example, it would be very helpful to develop policies aimed at creating fairer evaluation systems, re-examine the incentive structures, launch initiatives aimed at supporting researchers in leading full and balanced working lives, or promote more family-friendly policies. It is also essential to strengthen institutional support through guidance structures or the formalization of working and/or critical mentoring groups to guide junior faculty in their beginnings as a tool for support, survival, and resistance against the current system.

To conclude, although our study focuses on the Spanish context, our findings may have a wider impact, as the same type of policies are being developed across Europe due to an important standardization process (Ylijoki and Henriksson,2017; Brøgger,2019). Furthermore, it is important to mention that, as this is a unique case, the results shown here are not generalizable in the traditional sense. Nonetheless, they should serve as a further source of comprehensive knowledge that can be added to the findings of existing studies in this field (Giménez,2012). In other words, these results can contribute to illuminating the general from understanding the particular (Descombe,2010). Our findings could also be very useful for 1) Initiating a debate on the future of universities and science; and 2) Raising awareness among politicians and other agents of influence on evaluation systems. In particular, there is a need to warn of the adverse effects of the current evaluation criteria and to reinforce the idea that behind these impact factors there are professionals who wish to live a good social and professional life.

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